

NEWSLETTER

Welcome to CONCILIARE: Our Journey Begins

Welcome to the First Edition of the Conciliare Newsletter!

We are excited to launch the first edition of the Conciliare project newsletter! This platform will serve to promote the project, its partners, and ongoing research while extending communication to stakeholders and collaborators.

Published every two months, the newsletter will also function as an internal communication channel for the project teams, keeping everyone informed.

Stay Connected!

The Conciliare social media accounts are now live and accessible through the links provided in the email header. We encourage everyone to engage with and share our updates. The project website is currently under construction and will be launched soon.

PAST EVENTS

Since the Kickoff Meeting in Rome (March 2024), Conciliare members have participated in several key events:

- 15th Congress of Social Psychology (Brussels, July 2024)
- Colonial Legacies in Print: Textbooks from the 1950s to the Present Day (Coimbra, October 2024)
- Une approche sociétale des crises (Lyon, October 2024)
- Transmettre la mémoire – Journée d'étude (Mons, October 2024)
- La toponymie bruxelloise d'hier et de demain (Brussels, November 2024)

Last month, several Conciliare researchers came together at the International Conference "Decolonizing Museums and Resignifying Monuments" in Madrid. Photos and highlights from the event are already available on our social media channels. For more information about the presentations, visit the event page.

[READ MORE](#)

In future editions, we will share updates about upcoming events and milestones.
Thank you for joining us on this exciting journey. Let's keep building changes
together!

Isabel Macedo, Júlia Vilhena e Rosa Cabecinhas

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